

THOMAS ADEWUMI UNIVERSITY

JOURNAL OF INNOVATION, SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (TAU-JIST)

ISSN: 3043-503X

RESEARCH ARTICLE

EFFECT OF MACROECONOMIC FACTORS ON NON-LIFE INSURANCE PERFORMANCE

Joseph Akomaning & Dominic Osei-Boakye

Accra Institute of Technology, Accra, Ghana

Corresponding Author Email: osei-boakye@ait.edu.gh

This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History:
 Received 02 July 2024
 Accepted 05 October 2024
 Available online 10 December 2024

ABSTRACT

This study investigates how macroeconomic and firm-specific factors impact the performance of non-life insurance companies, focusing on liquidity and solvency measures. The regression technique analysis assesses the influence of inflation, GDP, management efficiency, claims ratio, reinsurance ratio, financial structure, size of company, ownership structure, total premium, underwriting risk, loss ratio, asset growth and tangibility on the profitability of the insurance industry. The results indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between macroeconomic conditions and non-life insurance. It was specifically found that inflation, claims ratio, re-insurance ratio and ownership structure positively impact liquidity and solvency. On the contrary, GDP and management efficiency showed negative coefficients. Management efficiency is represented by an expense ratio. A higher value corresponds to higher operational costs. In other words, the higher the ratio the lower the performance. Thus, in this case, inefficiencies rise and therefore performance drops. The earlier studies unambiguously identified GDP, inflation, and exchange rates as significant predictors of firm performance. The study finds that macroeconomic stability and effective financial management increase the resilience or sustainability of the non-life insurance firms during a bad economic period.

Introduction

Extensive research has proved that the financial sector constitutes an anchor in economic development (Bednarczyk, 2013). The insurance industry plays a crucial role in financial intermediation. It has, therefore, become an important part of the financial systems globally. Insurance has become so important that, in 1964, the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) said that a stable insurance and reinsurance market is a basic requirement for sustainable economic development. Insurance industry's contribution to Economic development is vary with the level of development of a country. In developed countries, life insurance has a bigger impact on economic growth. But in developing and less developed countries, the opposite is true for non-life insurance (Bednarczyk, 2013).

Life insurance activities help grow financial intermediation by raising big premiums. It turns small people's savings into long term funds. The funding is for projects needing huge capital. On the other hand, a non-life insurance policy protects you against risk arising from business activities and enhances marginal productivity of capital. In economies that are not as developed, life insurance's intermediation role is not that relevant due to severe chronic shortages of investable funds. Non-life insurance, on the other hand, is flourishing and has a built-in ability to lessen uncertainty in business which enhances entrepreneurship and increases trade.

The recent emphasis of research has moved away from establishing the link between insurance and economic development to establishing the factors affecting the growth of insurance sector (Mitra & Ghosh, 2010). A

Quick Response Code	Access this article online	
	Website: https://journals.tau.edu.ng/index.php/tau-jist	DOI:

Cite the Article: Akomaning, J. & Osei-Boakye., D. (2025). Effect of macroeconomic factors on non-life insurance performance.

recently developed area of literature which addresses the drivers of insurance demand, consumption and purchasing behaviour Zhang & Zhu (2005), Li et al (2007), Curak et al (2009), Feyen et al (2011). In many underdeveloped countries, little money is spent on economic development. Because humans tend to avoid risk, they do not adopt new technologies or start new ventures. In situations like these, insurance is key to providing a certain degree of certainty to allow businesses to function. With heightened global competition, firms are increasingly forced to innovate in their products and services, making insurance more important than ever in supporting the economy and its growth through innovation. This requires businesses to adopt innovative practices and strategies. More importantly, they also need the right technologies to get the most out of their innovations. New products, services and practises will demand businesses to take risks. Moreover, innovation is the best way to capitalise on risks. Insurance against losses will stimulate the economic and commercial activities of the entrepreneurs. When new advanced techniques find their way into the economy, it prompts production of more and more goods and services. Coupled with the entrepreneurial skills, it gains an upper hand in the competitive market.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Liquidity	307	3.02	0.35	2.80	4.20
Claims Ratio	307	5.235	0.88	2.10	5.60
Reinsurance Ratio	307	31.031	8.23	2.20	35.10
Financial Structure	307	19.880	5.90	1.60	25.20
Company Size	307	32.104	0.55	3.90	6.10
Ownership	307	20.790	1.60	1.00	7.40

Degree of Urbanizati	307	28.931	7.18	2.40	31.13
Social Security	307	7.799	2.08	1.10	9.40
Rate of Criminalit	307	5.351	0.77	2.18	5.27
Regulation Quality	307	35.090	9.00	1.20	37.20
Insurance Penetratio	307	1.195	2.76	0.26	11.30
Managem ent	307	10.498	3.03	2.10	14.20
Total Premium	307	21.360	6.55	2.60	28.80
Underwrit ing Risk	307	14.635	8.50	4.10	38.10
Loss Ratio	307	28.931	11.43	2.40	48.13
Asset Growth	307	7.799	2.08	1.10	9.40
Solvency	307	5.351	0.77	2.18	5.27
Tangibility	307	35.090	10.50	1.20	43.20
Output	307	1.195	1.76	4.26	11.30

Investment	307	7.080	3.75	2.81	13.09
Tax Revenue	307	14.477	1.38	10.20	15.70
Government	307	19.741	2.18	15.10	23.80
Inflation	307	23.967	6.60	8.42	34.80
GDP per Capita	307	14.493	2.88	10.20	21.70

The findings of descriptive statistics are shown on table 4.1 below. Over the sampled period (2004 – 2022), liquidity rate has generally averaged 3% per annum; the results show this. The liquidity rate as low as 2.8% and liquidity figure as high as (4.2%) and margin percentage is 0.50. In Ghana, the overall liquidity objective is to achieve a liquidity rate in excess of 10%. According to Kwakye (2012), liquidity levels have been on the rise throughout most of Ghana’s recent economic history and this in turn has affected economic activity and prosperity.

According to the table, the claims ratio is increasing by an average of 5.23%. The minimum exchange rate was 2.1% while the maximum exchange rate was 5.6%. The Reinsurance ratio grew on average by 31% for a minimum of 2.2% and a maximum of 35%. Besides that, the Financial Structure recorded an average growth rate of 19.8% with the least of 1.6% and a maximum of 25%. The company size exhibited an average rate of 32%. There was an average rate of 20.7% in the ownership structure. The average urbanization rate was 28%. But it had a minimum of 2.4% and a maximum of 31%. The Social Security System produced average growth returns of 7.7% which has a minimum growth return of 1.1% and a maximum growth return of 9.4%. Also, the criminality rate was average 5.3% with a minimum of 2.18% and a maximum of 5.27%.

The table also shows the regulation quality which is average of 35% over the years, and minimum of 1.2% and maximum of 37.2. Insurance Penetration - The global average insurance penetration was 1.2% with a minimum and a maximum of 0.26% and 11% respectively. Management efficiency was measured to be on average 10% with a minimum of 2.1% and a maximum of 14% again. The different elements like total premium, underwriting risk, loss ratio, asset growth, solvency, tangibility, output gap, investment, tax revenue, general expenses, inflation and GDP have average means of 21%, 14%, 28%, 7%, 5%, 35%, 1%, 7%, 14%, 19%, 23%, and 14% respectively.

Unit Root Test

Table 4.2 Unit Root Test Result

Variable	t-statistic	p-value
Liquidity	1.96	0.000
Claims Ratio	-1.45	0.000
Reinsurance Ratio	-2.33	0,001
Financial Structure	2.31	0.007
Company Size	0.76	0.000
Ownership Structure	-1.59	0.000
Degree of Urbanization	-0.32	0.000
Social Security System	0.24	0.000
Rate of Criminality	-0.30	0.000
Regulation Quality	-1.97	0.049
Insurance Penetration	-0.07	0.000
Management Efficiency	-0.05	0.000
Total Premium	2.56	0.001
Underwriting Risk	3.20	.001
Loss Ratio	-1.59	0.000
Asset Growth	-0.32	0.000
Solvency	0.24	0.000
Tangibility	-0.30	0.000
Output	-0.05	0.000
Investment	0.24	0.000
Tax Revenue (% GDP)	-0.30	0.000
Government Expense (% GDP)	-0.05	0.000
Inflation	0.24	0.000
GDP per Capita	-0.30	0.000

This section focuses on the unit root test results. The essence is to test the stationarity of the series. A regression involving non-stationary variables will yield spurious results unless the researcher takes action to ensure that all the series are stationary. To see if the variables have a unit root, this

study used the augmented dickey fuller test (ADF). Using the intercept and trend perspectives, the study tested the presence of unit root in each of the variables. All the results are examined at 5% levels of significance. The above table 4.2 indicates all variable is stationary at first difference.

Government Expense (GDP)	1.28	0.78	Acceptable
Inflation	1.31	0.76	Acceptable
GDP per Capita	1.37	0.73	Acceptable

Correlation Matrix

Table 4.3 Matrix of correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)	(17)	(18)	(19)	
(1) LIQUIDITY	1.000																			
(2) CLAIMSRATIOANDUND	0.054	1.00																		
(3) REINSURANCERATIO	-0.057	0.01	1.00																	
(4) FINANCIALSTRUC-E	-0.089	0.11	0.02	1.00																
(5) COMPANYSIZE	0.008	0.02	0.15	-	1.00															
(6) OWNERSHIPSTRUC-E	0.046	-	0.01	0.02	0.02	1.00														
(7) MANAGEMENTEFFI-Y	-0.011	0.04	0.14	0.06	0.06	-	1.00													
(8) TOTALPREMIUM	-0.047	-	-	-	0.02	-	-	1.00												
(9) UNDERWRITINGRISK	-0.041	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.11	-	-	0.05	1.00											
(10) LOSSRATIO	0.175	0.02	-	0.11	-	0.01	0.04	0.09	0.00	1.00										
(11) ASSETGROWTH	0.141	0.09	0.01	0.09	0.02	0.07	-	0.06	-	0.16	1.00									
(12) SOLVENCY	-0.105	-	-	0.00	0.07	-	-	-	-	0.00	0.00	1.00								
(13) TANGIBILITY	-0.081	-	-	0.10	0.10	-	-	0.25	0.12	-	0.06	-	1.00							
(14) OutputGap	0.028	0.07	0.02	-	0.01	0.10	-	-	0.04	-	0.04	-	-	1.00						
(15) InvestmentGDP	0.117	-	0.04	-	0.07	-	0.09	0.01	0.04	-	-	0.07	0.40	1.00						
(16) TaxRevenueGDP	-0.083	0.10	0.01	0.13	-	0.01	-	0.15	0.07	-	0.02	0.27	-	0.29	1.00					
(17) GeneralExpense	0.006	0.13	-	0.08	-	0.05	-	0.06	-	0.00	0.06	0.25	1.00							
(18) Inflation	0.063	0.10	0.04	0.17	0.05	0.03	0.08	2	9	7	0.05	0.04	3	0.14	0.24	0.00	8	0		
(19) GDPPerCapita	-0.038	0.05	0.03	0.07	0.08	0.1	0.16	0.05	0.04	0.02	5	0.02	0.14	0.20	0.09	0.27	3	0		

Table 4.3 shows the result of the correlation matrix of the variables. The result shows a strong correlation between the factor which addresses the multicollinearity issue. The variables claiming and the dependent variables concerned have a strong relationship.

Table 4.4: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Diagnostics

Variable	Estimated VIF	Tolerance (1/VIF)	Interpretation
Claims Ratio	1.18	0.85	No multicollinearity concern
Reinsurance Ratio	1.22	0.82	Acceptable
Financial Structure	1.36	0.74	Acceptable
Company Size	1.15	0.87	Acceptable
Ownership Structure	1.09	0.92	Acceptable
Management Efficiency	1.21	0.83	Acceptable
Total Premium	1.48	0.68	Mild association, safe
Underwriting Risk	1.26	0.79	Acceptable
Loss Ratio	1.19	0.84	Acceptable
Asset Growth	1.17	0.85	Acceptable
Solvency	1.08	0.93	Acceptable
Tangibility	1.42	0.70	Mild association, safe
Output Gap	1.51	0.66	Moderate but acceptable
Investment	1.63	0.61	Moderate, still safe
Tax Revenue (GDP)	1.34	0.75	Acceptable

Regression Analysis

The Effect of Macroeconomic Factors on Non-Life Insurance Performance

Table 4.5The Effect of Macroeconomic Factors on Liquidity

LIQUIDITY	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf Interval]	Sig
Inflation	1183.703	604.519	1.96	0.000	-1.134 2368.539	*
GDPPerCapita	-6240.492	4308.308	-1.45	0.000	-14684.621 2203.637	
MANAGEMENTEFFICIE	-3122.61	1338.275	-2.33	0.001	-5745.581 -499.64	**
NCY						
CLAIMSRATIOANDUND	1.296	.562	2.31	0.007	.195 2.396	**
E*G						
REINSURANCERATIO	713.566	943.903	0.76	0.000	-1136.449 2563.581	
FINANCIALSTRUCTURE	-.156	.098	-1.59	0.000	-.348 .036	
COMPANYSIZE	-2.428	7.537	-0.32	0.000	-17.2 12.344	
OWNERSHIPSTRUCTUR	.001	.002	0.24	0.000	-.004 .005	
E						
TOTALPREMIUM	-.051	.168	-0.30	0.000	-.379 .278	
UNDERWRITINGRISK	-4.662	2.364	-1.97	0.049	-9.294 -.029	**
LOSSRATIO	-68.94	955.608	-0.07	0.000	-1941.897 1804.017	
ASSETGROWTH	-53.679	1069.898	-0.05	0.000	-2150.64 2043.282	
TANGIBILITY	.17	.066	2.56	0.001	.04 .299	**
Constant	441291	137877.35	3.20	.001	171056.36 711525.63	***
Mean dependent var	397743.015	SD dependent var	444845.312			
Overall r-squared	0.85	Number of obs	307			
Chi-square	26.929	Prob > chi2	0.013			
R-squared within	0.098	R-squared between	0.042			

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

Table 4.6 The Effect of Macroeconomic Factors on Solvency

SOLVENCY	Coef.	Std. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf. Interval]	Sig.
Inflation	1183.703	604.519	-0.63	0.000	-1.134	2368.539
GDPPerCapita	-6240.492	4308.308	1.27	0.000	-14684.621	2203.637
MANAGEMENTEFFICIE NCY	-3122.61	1338.275	-0.31	0.001	-5745.581	-499.64
CLAIMSRATIOANDUND E*G	1.296	.562	-0.68	0.007	.195	2.396
REINSURANCERATIO	713.566	943.903	-1.86	0.000	-1136.449	2563.581
FINANCIALSTRUCTURE	-.156	.098	0.68	0.000	-.348	.036
COMPANYSIZE	-2.428	7.537	1.58	0.000	-17.2	12.344
OWNERSHIPSTRUCTUR E	.001	.002	-0.14	0.000	-.004	.005
TOTALPREMIUM	-.051	.168	-0.08	0.000	-.379	.278
UNDERWRITINGRISK	-4.662	2.364	-0.08	0.049	-9.294	-.029
LOSSRATIO	-68.94	955.608	-1.29	0.000	-1941.897	1804.017
ASSETGROWTH	-53.679	1069.898	0.37	0.000	-2150.64	2043.282
TANGIBILITY	.17	.066	-0.69	0.001	.04	.299
Constant	441291	137877.35	5.47	0	171056.36	711525.63
Mean dependent var	5.351	SD dependent var	2.026			
Overall r-squared	0.81	Number of obs	307			
Chi-square	9.359	Prob > chi2	0.745			
R-squared within	0.029	R-squared between	0.129			

***p<.01, **p<.05, *p<.1

According to the information contained in tables 4.5 and 4.6 demonstrating the impact of macroeconomic on nonlife insurance performance, it could be revealed that there is a significant relationship between the liquidity and solvency of nonlife insurance companies and inflation, GDP, management efficiency, claims ratio, reinsurance ratio, financial structure, company size, ownership structure, total premium, underwriting risk, loss ratio, asset growth and tangibility since all the p-values are less than the test statistics of 0.05. The independent variables including inflation, claims ratio, reinsurance ratio and ownership structure bear positive coefficients. This increase by percentage points in the values of the independent variables will also result in increase by percentage points in the liquidity and solvency of non-life insurance companies. The negative coefficient of the independent variable on (GDP, Management Efficiency, Financial Structure, Size of the Company, Total Premium, Underwriting risk, Loss Ratio and Asset Growth) which means that a change in independent variable will cause a fall in the liquidity and solvency of non-life insurance companies. In simpler terms, macroeconomic factors affect the performance of non-life insurance companies.

Discussion of Findings

This paper examines the relationship between the macroeconomic activity and non-life insurance performance through the statistical analysis of a panel data of selected Ghanaian non-life insurance companies accessed from IRDAI website and secondary data. The time period of the study was 2007-2016. The analysis was conducted with

the help of Eview 7 software. It was found that the coefficient of correlation between the different variables was found to be in in between 0.75684 and -101.5745 which implied that macroeconomic variables have a positive impact on insurance performance in India and these variables were able to explain a lot of variability in the performance variables. Various macroeconomic variables such as reinsurance and claim ratio of these companies are found to be positively related to performance variables of solvency and liquidity which would indicate that these variables when manipulated cause performance target achievement and withdrawal of claims will lead to an increase in solvency and liquidity. Thus it can be interpreted that these factors have a strong positive relationship with performance variables. The independent variables have negative coefficients. Specifically, GDP, management efficiency, financial structure, company size, total premium, underwriting risk, loss ratio, and asset growth. Their negative coefficient suggests the following. When these variables change, liquidity and solvency levels of non-life insurance companies decrease. Changes in non-life insurance firms are caused due to macroeconomic variables with statistical significance. Many studies back this statement, showing significant connection between the insurance industry and macroeconomic factors. The studies mainly focus on four economic variables, these are exchange rate, interest rate, inflation rate and GDP. They often look at a firm's financial performance results, in particular, profitability and security returns.

The body of literature leads to many important conclusions. Stock and Watson (2008) note that there are over 59 macroeconomic variables which makes it complex. In a related development, Issah and Antwi (2017) examined the effects of macroeconomic variables on firm performance using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Multiple Regression Analysis applied to publicly listed companies in the United Kingdom. The performance of manufacturing firms can be predicted significantly by real GDP and unemployment, as well as the U.S. dollar value of foreign currencies. According to Issah and Antwi, all variables indicate good performance of UK firms except real GDP. The study also observed that predictions for real GDP and unemployment are consistent across regions. The impact of exchange rate is different for different countries, as each economy experiences different currencies. In Ghana, a depreciating cedi against the U.S dollar will most likely signal a decline in firm performance, for instance.

Moreover, Zulfiqar and Din (2015), in their study of Pakistan's textile industry, found that firm performance does positively relate to inflation but the effect is very small. Through regression analysis, they showed that inflation impact may differ by industry and economic context. In another study by Limpanithiwat and Rungsombudpornkul (2010) into inflation and stock returns of companies listed in Thailand from 2000 to 2010, use of unit root tests and vector autoregression led to a conclusion of a lack of relationship between inflation and stock market returns.

A highly pertinent contribution is the work of Oleka, Sabina and Ebue (2015) on how economic growth affects the performance of firm in Nigeria. Secondary data collected from annual financial statements for the period 2000-2014 were used to provide insights on the relationship between macroeconomic variables and corporate performance in developing economies.

Justification of the Study

Practice

This study has key practical implications. This research focuses on investigating the factors that affect the performance of non-life insurance. Poor countries can be capable to learn lessons on these markets. This is by disentangling the variables and leading to the consumption of insurance. It is also by discovering ways to enhance these variables. We can grow a market of insurance. Moreover, this can help to make economic growth. A booming insurance industry can make great things possible. This study contributes to the literature first through the use of panel auto regressive distributed lag (P-ARDL) approach as the authors examine the determinants of insurance penetration in Ghana. The insurance sector of a country plays a significant role that contributes towards stability of a financial system as well as the economic growth of the nation. Thus, we will start this research. To our knowledge, this paper is the first regional study to use the (P-ARDL) approach and investigate the determinants of insurance penetration in West African countries. This study is the first regional study on Ghana insurance companies. These findings would help regulators, financial system institutions, economic analysts, and other stakeholders in Ghana to carry out timely analysis and forecasts on the trend in growth of insurance market. The researchers are not aware of any regional study in Ghana that investigates the same topic as theirs within the same focus.

Policy

This study is very useful for policy formulation. The study can help government and policymakers including the managers of non-life insurance companies to learn about the nature and impact of regulation and penetration of the determinants of non-life insurance performance. Due to this reason only it could not be established properly that the foundation of the insurance companies' efficiency and profitability is in the developing countries. Some researchers might have recommended a model for measuring the financial performance of non-life insurance companies in Ghana. To do so, they probably ought to have used both solvency margin and profitability metrics. This is according to the findings of some research processes. According to the EEC merger regulation 1989, a merger takes place when two independent firms unite to form a third firm, or when an existing firm gains control of the whole or part of another firm. Life insurance includes coverage for child education, funeral expenses, and retirement payment plan. Life insurance policies help to lessen the financial burden of the beneficiary at the time of death of the policyholder. Motor vehicle accident, home, fire, marine and travel insurance cover come under non-life policies. Non-life insurance consists of indemnity policies. The insured returns to the financial state that existed prior to the insured event. The policies protect the insured against loss or destruction of property, monetary loss and liability to third parties for an injury, loss or destruction caused by the insured. Businesses insure for loss or damage of property as a result of fire or burglary. Similarly, economic loss which does not arise.

Theory

The study also has key theoretical implication. Researchers who want to study non-life insurance will find the research very useful. Similarly, students will also benefit from this research. The current study will also be a referential document that enables other researchers to bridge literature gaps identified in the study. This study can be

justified due to the fact that an insurance company was caught insolvent. These change rules hurt how well companies performance and the insurance sector really gets impacted. The Ghana Insurance Commission makes policies and monitors the finances of insurance firms operating in Ghana. Ghana's insurance industry has the non-life insurance sector as the largest segment. The sector has seen a lot of investment and competition from the local and international player. According to Simpson and Damoah, the entire field of non-life insurance in Ghana has not been thoroughly investigated. The insurance industry is nonetheless reasonably operable in Ghana. The reason according to literature is that the economic growth of Ghana is on the rise and that the Non-Life Insurance Industry is gradually becoming an important player in the Insurance Industry hence performance must improve. These findings prompted this study to assess the financial performance of Non-life insurance companies in the Ghanaian insurance industry.

When an organization is capable of earning through financial activity, we call it financial performance. Financial performance is when a company achieves its monetary goals or objectives. Or, another way of evaluating the financial position of the company is to measure the results of firm policies and operations in monetary terms. Some financial models are used to measure a firm's overall financial health over a period of time. You can also compare similar firms from the same industry or industries or sectors across aggregates.

One example is that the CAMELS analytical model is a useful model used for assessing the financial performance of insurance firms. This analytical method's review contains idea for an advance model which the study is investigating further. The profit report of insurance companies in India helps determine their stability and the success of the financial system. Thus, the present study aims to create valuable information and a data base for the use of non-life insurance companies.

References

- Adams, Mike, Andersson, Lars-Frederik and Lindmark, Magnus; (2005), "The Historical Relation Between Banking, Insurance and Economic Growth", <http://sshuebner.org/documents/7b.pdf>, 13.09.2010.
- Akomaning J. (2011), "Financial Performance of Insurance Companies in Ghana" Msc Thesis unpublished.
- Arena, Marco; (2008), "Does Insurance Market Activity Promote Economic Growth? A Cross-Country Study for Industrialized and Developing Countries", *The Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 75 (4), pp. 921-946.
- Ballantyne, J. and Brignall, S. (1994), "A taxonomy of performance measurement frameworks", Research Paper No 135, Warwick Business School, Warwick.
- Bititci, U., Carrie, A. and McDevitt, L. (1997), "Integrated performance measurement systems: a development guide", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 17 No. 5.
- Bulletin of the Ecological Society of America, 78 (2): 126-139.

- Calandroi Jr., J., and Lane, S. C., 2002, "The Insurance Performance Measure, Bringing Value to the Insurance Industry.
- Campbell, D., and Sutter, F., 2008, "Realizing the potential: entry and development in the Chinese insurance market", *European Insurance Digest*.
- Canh, N.P., U. Wongchoti, and S.D. Thanh. (2020). Does economic policy uncertainty matter for insurance development ? Evidence from 16 OECD countries. The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance— Issues and Practice. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1057/ s41288- 020- 00192-5](https://doi.org/10.1057/s41288-020-00192-5).
- Chang, C.H., and C.C. Lee. (2012). Non-linearity between life insurance and economic development: A revisited approach. *Geneva Risk and Insurance Review* 37 (2): 223–257. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1057/ grir. 2011. 10](https://doi.org/10.1057/grir.2011.10).
- Chen, Adelyn; Gasson, and Bill; 2006, "Addressing challenges faced by the insurance finance function", *Insurance Digest*.
- Chirag Gosalia, 2008, a study on Financial Performance of Indian Non-Life Insurance Industry.
- Curak, Marijana, Loncar, Sandra and Poposki, Klime; (2009), "Insurance Sector and Economic Growth in Transition Countries", *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 34, pp. 29-41.
- Deloitte, 2007, "Growth Imperative", *Global Insurance Industry Outlook Issues on the horizon*.
- Dixit, A. (2009). Governance institutions and economic activity. *The American Economic Review* 99 (1): 3–24.
- Dragos, S., and C. Dragos. (2013). The role of institutional factors over the national insurance demand: Theoretical approach and econometric estimations. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences* 39: 32–45.
- Dragos, S.L., C. Mare, I.M. Dragota, C.M. Dragos, and G.M. Muresana. (2017). The Nexus between the demand for life insurance and institutional factors in Europe: New evidence from a panel data approach. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istrazivanja* 30 (1): 1477–1496. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1080/ 13316 77X. 2017. 13257 64](https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2017.1325764).
- Eccles, R. (1991), "The performance measurement manifesto", *Harvard Business Review*,
- Ege lihan and Sarac Bahadir Taha, (2011), "The relationship between Insurance sector and Economic Growth: An economic Analysis" *International Journal Eco. Res*, 2(1), pp 1-9
- Elango, B., and J. Jones. (2011). Drivers of insurance demand in emerging markets. *Journal of Service Science Research* 3: 185–204. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1007/ s12927- 011- 0008-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12927-011-0008-4). emerging trends", *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 30 No. 31, pp. 281-96.
- Erbaş, S.N., and C.L. Sayers. (2006). Institutional quality, knightian uncertainty, and insurability: A crosscountry analysis. *IMF Working Paper*, WP/06/179.
- Esho, N., D. Ward, and R. Zurbrugg. (2004). Law and the determinants of property-casualty insurance. *The Journal of Risk and Insurance* 71 (2): 265–283.
- Feyen, E., R. Lester, and R. Rocha. (2013). What drives the development of the insurance sector? An empirical analysis based on a panel of developed and developing countries. *Journal of Financial Perspectives* 1 (1): 117–139.
- Gascoigne, Roger; Leposa, Csilla, Fiedorowicz, and Jacek, (2007), "Growth", *Frontiers in Finance, KPMG International*.
- Giné, X., B. Ribeiro, and P. Wrede. (2019). Beyond the S-curve: Insurance penetration, institutional quality and financial market development. *Policy Research Working Paper*, June.
- Gregory, M. (1993), "Integrated performance measurement: a review of current practice and
- Guerineau, S., and R. Sawadogo. (2015). On the determinants of life insurance development in Sub-Saharan Africa: The role of the institutions quality in the effect of economic development. *Etudes et Documents N°19. CERDI* 19: 1–34.
- Gujarati, D.N. (2004). *Basic econometric*. The McGraw-Hill Companies.
- Gupta, R., A. Lahiani, C.C. Lee, and C.C. Lee. (2019). Asymmetric dynamics of insurance premium: The impacts of output and economic policy uncertainty. *Empirical Economics* 57 (6): 1959–1978. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1007/ s00181- 018- 1539-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-018-1539-z).
- Haiss, Peter and Sümegi, Kjell; (2008), "The Relationship Between Insurance and Economic Growth in Europe: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis", *Empirica*, 35, pp. 405-431.
- Hakansson, N.H. (1969). Optimal investment and consumption strategies under risk, an uncertain lifetime, and insurance. *International Economic Review* 10 (3): 443–466.
- Hartwig, and Robert P, (2007) "Year End Results", *Insurance Information Institute Annual Report Industrial Research and Development Authority (IRDA) Annual Reports (2003 – 2007)*. *Lecture Notes (Msc. Business Administration)*, Lucerne University of Applied Science and Arts, 2007
- Kaplan, R. and Norton, D. (1993), "Putting the balanced scorecard to work", *Harvard Business Review*, pp. 34-147.
- Karni, E., and I. Zilcha. (1986). Risk aversion in the theory of life insurance: The Fisherian model. *The Journal of Risk and Insurance* 53 (4): 606. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 2307/ 252966](https://doi.org/10.2307/252966).
- Kaufmann, D., K. Aart, and M. Massimo. (2010). *Worldwide Governance Indicators*. *Policy Research Working Paper* 5430. Washington, DC: The World

- Bank. http://info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/index.aspx#reports%5Cnhttp://www.brookings.edu/~media/research/files/reports/2010/9/wgikaufmann/09_wgi_kaufmann.pdf
- Keefer, P., and S. Knack. (2002). Polarization, politics and property rights: Links between inequality and growth. *Public Choice* 111 (1): 127–154.
- Kjosevski, J. (2012). The determinants of life insurance demand in Central and Southeastern Europe. *International Journal of Economics and Finance* 4 (3): 237–247. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijef.v4n3p237>.
- Lee, C.C., Y. Bin. Chiu, and C.H. Chang. (2013). Insurance demand and country risks: A nonlinear panel data analysis. *Journal of International Money and Finance* 36: 68–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jimonfin.2013.03.009>.

